

Heat of Transport of Aqueous Ammonium Chloride and Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate in a Saline Soil

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Manuscript received 11 June 1986, accepted 13 November 1986

Thermal diffusion of aqueous ammonium chloride and potassium dihydrogen phosphate at different mean concentrations was studied by using a three-chamber non-isothermal cell, and the corresponding heat of transport values ($\hat{Q}$) were calculated by using a relation based on irreversible thermodynamics. The graphical extrapolation of $\hat{Q}$ to zero concentration yielded the heat of transport value at infinite dilution ($\hat{Q}^\circ$). The results are qualitatively interpreted in terms of the difference between the 'local' degree of ordering in water in the bulk solution as compared to that in contact with the soil particles.

THERE have been earlier reports¹⁻⁷ of studies of thermal diffusion of water in soils and clays. Similar investigations involving aqueous solutions are, however, lacking. Very recently, thermal diffusion of aqueous zinc sulphate in soil has been reported by Sanyal and Bandyopadhyay⁸. The present paper looks at the non-isothermal diffusion of aqueous ammonium chloride and potassium dihydrogen phosphate at various concentrations in a saline soil. The theoretical treatment adopted is an extension of that recently proposed by Mukherjee and Sanyal⁷ for dealing with diffusion of a solution through an 'open' membrane subjected to a temperature gradient.

Experimental

The soil used was a saline soil from Canning (24-parganas), having pH, organic carbon, clay content, C.E.C., E.C. of (1 : 2) soil extract and water holding capacity of 8.0, 0.74%, 20.6%, 11.2 meq/100 g, 4.2 mmho cm⁻¹, 68.8%, respectively.

The diffusion cell was the same as used earlier⁶. It consisted of a three-chamber perspex box (well insulated against ambient temperature fluctuations) in which the soil chamber was sandwiched between two terminal solution chambers. The soil, moistened to the desired degree (70% of the water holding capacity), was placed inside the central chamber with NH₄Cl solution (0.05 M) in the terminal chambers by taking due care to eliminate any entrapped air. The whole set-up was placed inside an air-thermostat maintained at the mean temperature of the experiment. On applying the appropriate temperature gradient, thermocouple readings were monitored and once the steady state was attained as indicated by the solution levels in the two (short) terminal U-tubes (which lead to ΔP) becoming stationary, suitable aliquots were withdrawn from both the solution chambers, and the concentration

differences of NH₄Cl were measured spectrophotometrically at 415 nm using Nessler's reagent. The hydrostatic pressure difference (ΔP) was recorded by noting the solution levels in the two terminal U-tubes after making due allowance for unequal thermal expansion of solution in the terminal chambers. Thermal diffusion of aqueous NH₄Cl at several other mean concentrations, such as 0.2, 0.15 and 0.1 M was studied in the same way and the corresponding heat of transport values evaluated.

The heat of transport ($\hat{Q}$) of aqueous NH₄Cl was calculated by using equation (1) based on non-equilibrium thermodynamics⁷,

$$\hat{Q} = RT^2 \sigma_1 \beta_1 - T(\bar{V}_1 + \bar{V}_0) \left(\frac{\Delta P - \Delta \pi}{\Delta T} \right)_{st} \quad (1)$$

where, ΔP and $\Delta \pi$ are the hydrostatic and osmotic pressure differences between the two terminal solution chambers, respectively, $\bar{V}_1$ and $\bar{V}_0$ are the respective partial molal volumes of the solute and solvent, while σ_1 , the Soret coefficient of the solute, is given by

$$\sigma_1 = - \frac{1}{m_1} \left(\frac{\Delta m}{\Delta T} \right)_{st}$$

m_1 being the mean molality; β_1 is a thermodynamic factor given by

$$\beta_1 = \left(1 + \frac{\Delta \ln \gamma}{\Delta \ln m} \right)_{st}, \quad \gamma \text{ being the activity coefficient}$$

of the solute. The partial molal volumes were obtained from the corresponding density data while the osmotic pressure differences ($\Delta \pi$) were calculated from the measured Δm values at the steady state.

The heat of transport ($\hat{Q}$) so obtained is known to be sensitive to the nature of interactions in the system^{8,9}, and is formally defined to be the amount of heat absorbed per mole of a diffusing substance from the region it leaves, and released in the region it moves into under isothermal conditions⁸.

TABLE 1—HEAT OF TRANSPORT OF AQUEOUS NH_4Cl AND KH_2PO_4 IN SALINE SOIL

Sl. no.	Concn. m	T K	ΔT K	Δm $\times 10^{-4}$	σ_1 $\times 10^3 \text{ K}^{-1}$	β_1	$\frac{RT^2}{\sigma_1 \beta_1}$ kJ mol^{-1}	$\bar{V}_1$ ml mol^{-1}	$\bar{V}_0$ ml mol^{-1}	$\hat{Q}$ kJ mol^{-1}	$\hat{Q}^\circ$ kJ mol^{-1}
Aqueous NH_4Cl											
1.	0.20			9.06	0.581		0.408			0.407 (± 0.007)	
2.	0.15			12.27	1.05		0.786			0.726 (± 0.189)	
3.	0.10	306.4	7.8	27.83	3.57	0.899 1	2.504	36.80	18.10	2.49 (± 0.393)	13.5
4.	0.05			31.33	8.03		5.637			5.63 (± 0.311)	
Aqueous KH_2PO_4											
5.	0.100			17.00	3.04		2.02			2.01 (± 0.407)	
6.	0.075			19.27	4.59		3.04			3.03 (± 0.174)	
7.	0.050	307.3	5.6	27.08	9.67	0.844 1	6.41	38.10	18.10	6.39 (± 1.31)	47.2
8.	0.025			30.17	21.55		14.28			14.16 (± 0.656)	

The thermal diffusion experiments in the same soil of aqueous potassium dihydrogen phosphate at 0.1, 0.075, 0.05 and 0.025 M were also performed, and the corresponding $\hat{Q}$ values were evaluated with the aid of equation (1). Subsequent plotting of these $\hat{Q}$ values against $\sqrt{m}$ in both the cases yielded the corresponding $\hat{Q}^\circ$ values on graphical extrapolation to infinite dilution.

Results and Discussion

The heat of transport ($\hat{Q}$) values of aqueous NH_4Cl and KH_2PO_4 are recorded in Table 1. Each value is a mean of at least three determinations under identical conditions, and the corresponding error estimates (standard deviations) are given within parenthesis below the appropriate $\hat{Q}$ in the Table 1. The positive $\hat{Q}$ values correspond to an absorption of heat behind the diffusing entity and a liberation ahead in course of diffusional transport through the soil. Thus, these positive $\hat{Q}$ values point towards the disruption of water-structure in contact with soil particles (having relatively low clay and organic matter contents) as compared to the situation in the bulk solution. A higher heat of transport for KH_2PO_4 than that for NH_4Cl (especially at lower concentrations) obviously arises from a stronger orienting influence of polyvalent phosphate ion as compared to that of chloride, which widens the difference in the degrees of ordering of water molecules between the soil chamber and the bulk solution phase. The fall in $\hat{Q}$ values with increasing concentrations in both the cases (Table 1) may be attributed to the fact that long-range ion-solvent interactions in dilute electrolyte

solutions cause positive contribution towards $\hat{Q}$ values, and that these contributions are likely to fall rapidly with increasing concentrations owing to a mutual screening effect of the ions as proposed by Gurney⁹. The latter causes a corresponding lowering of $\hat{Q}$. Figs. 1 and 2 are the plots of $\hat{Q}$ vs $\sqrt{m}$

Fig 1

Fig. 2

for aqueous NH_4Cl and KH_2PO_4 , respectively. The Q° values at infinite dilution turn out (on graphical extrapolation) to be 13.5 and 47.2 kJ mol^{-1} , respectively, for the NH_4Cl and KH_2PO_4 solutions.

References

1. J. W. GARY and S. A. TAYLOR, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1962, **26**, 423, 417.
2. J. W. GARY and S. A. TAYLOR, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1964, **28**, 167.
3. R. P. TRIPATHI and B. P. GHILDYAL, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1978, **26**, 813.
4. S. K. SANYAL, B. G. MAITRA and M. ADHIKARI, *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1983, **31**, 464.
5. S. K. SANYAL and M. ADHIKARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 1071.
6. S. K. SANYAL and S. BANDYOPADHYAY, *Indian Agric.*, 1985, **29**, 159.
7. A. K. MUKHERJEE and S. K. SANYAL, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 761.
8. J. N. AGAR, *Adv. Electrochem Electrochem. Eng.*, 1968, **3**, 81.
9. R. W. GURNEY, "Ionic Processes in Solution", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1963.